

Adaptive Upper Limb Robot Based Training Protocol for Multiple Sclerosis Rehabilitation

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Abstract—The use of robotic devices for tailored rehabilitation and sensorimotor function assessment has gained great interest. This study shows an innovative upper limb robotic training protocol for persons with Multiple Sclerosis where the 8-week training involved a robot-assisted eccentric tracking task using the less affected limb, preceded and followed by robotic assessments and strength measurements. Results show significant improvement in tracking skill performance and muscle strength, suggesting that this robotic training could improve motor control and strength in MS.

Keywords—robotic rehabilitation, upper limb, multiple sclerosis

I. INTRODUCTION

Multiple Sclerosis (MS) is a debilitating disease of the central nervous system that can impair strength and motor function, and results in upper limb disability in 75% of cases. A lack of hand function and decreased grip strength hinder an individual's ability to perform activities of daily living (ADLs) which often require coordinated wrist movements. Although it is a bilateral disease, one limb is often more affected, leading to functional asymmetries and potential disuse of the latter. Recently, there has been a growing interest in using robotic devices alongside traditional therapy to individualize upper limb rehabilitation protocols and provide assessment strategies for monitoring progress. Robotics can offer real-time feedback during task performance, assess the sensorimotor function of one's limb, and use assistive forces or low resistive loads at high repetitions to promote neuroplasticity [1]. In [2] we presented a work aimed at implementing and testing a preliminary adaptive unilateral training program, utilizing a novel haptic wrist robot for tailored therapy on persons with Multiple Sclerosis (PwMS). The aim was to investigate the impact of this upper limb robotic training on both strength and robotically assessed outcomes and to evaluate the effects on both the trained and untrained limbs on a population of PwMS compared with a non-MS control group. In [2], the MS group performed the training on the self-reported most affected limb. The goal of the present work is to integrate the results of the previous work with the ones obtained considering a second group of PwMS, which performed the training on the self-reported less affected limb. As in the previous work, we hypothesized that the robotic outcomes would be able to find initial differences between trained and untrained limbs and thus identify the self-reported most affected limb compared to the less affected limb. As in [2], we also expected a significant improvement in the function (robotic performance outcomes and maximum strength) of the trained limb from pre- to post-intervention in the considered population.

II. METHODS

A. Participants

Participants gave their informed consent to take part in this study approved by the Brock University Research Ethics Board (for Human Participant Research) - REB 22-005.

In addition to the non-MS group (control, C) and to the PwMS group (MS1) presented in [2], a second group of PwMS (MS2) participated in this study. The MS1 phenotypes included 3 participants with relapsing-remitting MS (RRMS), 2 with primary progressive MS (PPMS), 3 with secondary progressive MS (SPMS), and 1 with clinically isolated syndrome (CIS). For the MS2 group, there were 3 participants with RRMS, 1 with PPMS, and 3 with SPMS. Participants in the MS1 group performed the training with their self-reported most-affected limb, while the MS2 group used their less-affected limb. Control group participants trained with their dominant limb. Further details are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. Participants characteristics (M = male, F = female, R = right, L = left, EDSS = Expanded Disability Status Scale)

Group	Sex	Age [yrs]	Trained side	EDSS
MS1	2M/7F	56.78 ± 10.51	4R/5L	4.17 ± 2.13
MS2	3M/4F	61.71 ± 6.34	4R/3L	5.29 ± 1.22
Control	8F	45.63 ± 17.73	7R/1L	/

B. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup includes a robotic wrist manipulator known as WRISTBOT [3], a three-degree-of-freedom device designed for wrist flexion/extension (F/E), radial/ulnar deviation (RD/UD), and pronation/supination (P/S), with a human-like range of motion (ROM) along all planes. Additionally, an integrated virtual reality environment provided visual feedback to the user.

C. Experimental Protocol and Data Analysis

As in [2], robotic assessments and strength measurements were conducted both before (PRE) and after (POST) a designated period of robotic training. The training period lasted 8 weeks, during which participants performed a robot-based task three times a week for approximately a 25-minute training session consisting of 5 sets. The robot-based training task targeted strength and motor control. Participants used their training limb to move the device's handle and track a dot on a monitor across four wrist directions (F/E, RD/UD). The task induced eccentric contractions, with participants resisting the force in a slow, controlled motion. The force, implemented as a virtual linear spring, was initially set to 40% of each participant's Maximum Voluntary Force (MVF), measured in all four directions using a dynamometer before the training session. The force was then dynamically adjusted during

training, increasing or decreasing by 5% steps based on performance, indicated by the Tracking Error [4].

PRE- and POST-training assessments of both limbs included strength measures that consisted of maximum isometric force (N) along the 4 directions (F/E/RD/UD), and 3 robotic tasks: 1) Active ROM: the maximum rotation ($^{\circ}$) each participant could reach along F/E/RD/UD [4]; 2) Wrist Position Matching: involved replicating a previously assumed joint configuration along F/E without visual feedback. Position sense was assessed using *Matching Error* (ME°) and *Error Bias* (EB°) [5]; 3) Active Tracking: the goal was to follow a moving target along an 8-shaped trajectory. Eye-hand accuracy was evaluated through the *Tracking Error* (TE°), which represents the ability to closely follow the target, and the *Figural Error* (FE°) which is related to spatial tracking accuracy [4].

Data were analyzed offline using custom code in Python. Since data were not normally distributed, Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Tests were conducted to perform pairwise comparisons. Significance was set to $p < 0.05$.

III. RESULTS

For Active ROM, the trained limbs of the MS group (MS2-T), had an initial median ROM comparable to the unimpaired. No significant differences were found between the trained and untrained (MS2-NT) limbs before the training, and no significant change from pre- to post-training performance was found when the trained limb was assessed.

For the Wrist Position Matching task, no significant differences in any of the comparisons made were found in ME or EB for the MS2 group in either the F or E directions.

Figure 1. Tracking Error. Pre-post training behavior of Control and MS groups.

Regarding the Active Tracking, in FE, no initial differences were found between the trained and untrained limbs of the MS2 group. A significant error reduction was identified from pre- to post-training when the trained limb was assessed (MS2-T PRE vs MS2-T POST: $W=26.0, p=0.023$). As for TE, no initial differences were found between the trained and untrained limbs of the MS2 group. However, as shown in Figure 1 with a red star, a significant error reduction was identified from pre- to post-training when the trained limb was assessed (MS2-T PRE vs MS2-T POST: $W=28.0, p=0.008$).

Concerning the strength measures, the comparison between trained and untrained limbs in the pre-training showed no significant differences. The improvement from pre- to post-training for the trained limb was significant in all the directions (F: $W=0.0, p=0.008$; E: $W=0.0, p=0.008$; RD: $W=0.0, p=0.008$; UD: $W=0.0, p=0.008$).

IV. DISCUSSION

This work aimed to complement the previous research [2] that focused on creating and testing an adaptive upper-limb training program to exploit robotics for MS rehabilitation by incorporating the results from another group of PwMS who

performed the training on their self-reported less affected limb. As in [2], the main findings pointed out that taking part in the robotic training program could enhance upper limb motor control and muscle strength in PwMS. In both works, no significant improvements were observed in proprioception and ROM. Similarly to [2], baseline ROM results for the limb to be trained for the MS2 group were comparable to the non-MS participants, consequently, there was no improvement from pre- to post-training.

Results of the Wrist Position Matching task showed that there were no significant initial differences between trained and untrained limbs in any of the robotic outcomes, differently from [2] in which a significant difference in the EB outcome was found for the MS1 group. Results showed no improvements in proprioception from pre- to post-training. The training protocol did not specifically train proprioception, which may explain the lack of pre/post changes.

Significant improvements from pre- to post-training were found in tracking performance for both outcomes FE and TE in the trained limb, differently from [2] in which an improvement was found only for FE. This suggests that using the less-affected limb facilitated their accuracy in following not only the trajectory but also the kinematics of the target.

The protocol involved strength measurements and, similarly to [2], significant differences from pre- to post-training were found in all the directions: F increased by 35%, E by 49%, RD by 49% and UD by 41%. This highlights that this type of training successfully targeted and improved maximum isometric strength in PwMS. In contrast to [2] in which initial differences between the trained and untrained limbs were found for the E and RD directions in the MS1 group, the MS2 group reported no initial difference. This result, which also occurred in the proprioceptive task, could indicate that, given the higher EDSS level of the MS2 group with respect to the MS1, different outcome measures highlighting these differences are needed.

The results of this preliminary study will be useful as a basis for future tests and studies on PwMS. One aspect that could be investigated is cross-education (CE), a neurophysiological phenomenon where training one limb leads to strength and skill improvements in the untrained contralateral limb [6]. Evaluating these crossover effects could help determine the feasibility of training the opposing limb when the most affected limb cannot be directly trained.

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